

TERPENODIS. PART IV. A NEW SYNTHESIS OF
dl-CARVOTANACETONE

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A new synthesis of *dl*-carvotanacetone has been achieved.

Carvotanacetone is a monocyclic terpene ketone which occurs in nature in its *dextro* form in the oils derived from *Blumea malcomii* and *Blumea criorantha* (Simonsen and Rau, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 876; Schimmel's report, 1937, p. 8). It has also been isolated in the *dl*-form from the high boiling fraction of Thuja oil (Wallach, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 275, 183). On the basis of chemical evidence this natural ketone was formulated as (III).

The structure (III) was later confirmed by Frank and Hall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1645) by a direct synthesis of the *dl*-ketone through the diketone (I). We now record an alternative elegant synthesis of the racemate of the same naturally occurring ketone. The new approach is based on an earlier method developed by Frank and Hall (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of enolic ethers from cyclic diketones.

5-*iso*Propyl-1:3-cyclohexan-dione, the starting material in the present scheme, was prepared exactly according to Frank and Hall (*loc. cit.*). It was methylated with methyl iodide and aqueous potassium hydroxide (cf. Stetter, Kessler and Meisel, *Ber.*, 1954, 87, 1617). Whereas Frank *et al.* could not convert this 2-substituted diketone (I) into its enolic ether, we succeeded in doing so by using *isobutyl* alcohol in place of ethyl alcohol, which was employed by them. The *isobutyl* enolic ether (II) was then allowed to react with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by decomposition of the reduced product with dilute sulphuric acid (cf. Mukherji, Sharma and Vig, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 857). The ketone (III), *dl*-carvotanacetone, was formed in good yield. The identity of the synthetic product was established through its derivatives and ultraviolet spectrum.

EXPERIMENTAL*

5-*iso*Propyl-2-methyl-1:3-cyclohexan-dione (I).—To a solution of 5-*iso*propyl-1:3-cyclohexan-dione (15.4 g., 0.1M; Frank *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) in aqueous potash (5.6 g., 0.1M,

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

dissolved in 30 c.c. of water) was added dropwise, with stirring, methyl iodide (25 g.) at ordinary temperature. The mixture was stirred for 3 hours and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was extracted with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution several times. The bicarbonate solution was acidified with HCl and the resulting precipitate was recrystallised from aqueous acetone, yield 10 g. (60%), m.p. 179.81°. Frank and Hall (*loc. cit.*) reported m.p. 178-81°.

2-Methyl-3-isobutoxy-5-isopropyl-2-cyclohexenone (II).—A mixture of the diketone (I, 16.8 g.), isobutyl alcohol (30 g.), dry benzene (200 c.c.) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (200 mg.) was refluxed under a modified Dean and Stark apparatus. It was heated for 5 hours in an oil-bath and when no more water separated, it was cooled. The free acid in the mixture was neutralised with sodium ethoxide and then it was diluted with water. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous portion was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. It was stripped off the solvent and the residue distilled under vacuum, b.p. 145-50°/5 mm, yield 14 g. (62%), n_D^{15} 1.486. (Found: C, 74.82; H, 10.62. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 10.71%).

5-isopropyl-2-methyl-2-cyclohexenone (*dl*-Carvotanacetone) (III).—To a well-stirred solution of lithium aluminium hydride (0.95 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.) at ordinary temperature was added dropwise a solution of 2-methyl-3-isobutoxy-5-isopropyl-2-cyclohexenone (11.2 g.) in ether (50 c.c.) at such a rate as to maintain a gentle refluxing. The mixture was stirred for half an hour after the addition and then decomposed with 10 c.c. of 10% H_2SO_4 . It was kept as such for 2 hours and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the product distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 98-100°/7 mm, yield 6.2 g. (80%), n_D^{20} 1.4790 (Brühl, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1225, reported n_D^{20} 1.4805); λ_{max}^{alc} 235 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.14) (Frank *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report for *dl*-carvotanacetone λ_{max}^{alc} 237 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.19). (Found: C, 78.58; H, 10.34. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way and crystallised from alcohol, melted at 178° (Baeyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1923, recorded m.p. 177-79° for *dl*-carvotanacetone derivative). (Found: N, 19.87. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{15}ON_3$: N, 20.08%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and crystallised as red micro-crystals from ethyl acetate, m.p. 191° (Short and Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1044, reported for *dl*-carvotanacetone 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 191-92°). (Found: N, 16.59. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 16.85%).

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